

H2020 - Research and Innovation Action

APPLICATE^{*}

Advanced Prediction in Polar regions and beyond: Modelling, observing system design and Linkages associated with a Changing Arctic climaTE

Grant Agreement No: 727862

Deliverable No. 7.3 update

User-Engagement Plan

Submission of Deliverable

Work Package	WP7 User engagement, dissemination and training		
Deliverable No	D7.3 update		
Deliverable title	User-engagement plan update		
Version	2		
Status	Final		
Dissemination level	PU - Public		
Lead Beneficiary	13 - AP		
Contributors	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 1 – AWI	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 2 – BSC	<input type="checkbox"/> 3 - ECMWF
	<input type="checkbox"/> 4 – UiB	<input type="checkbox"/> 5 – UNI Research	<input type="checkbox"/> 6 – MET Norway
	<input type="checkbox"/> 7 – Met Office	<input type="checkbox"/> 8 – UCL	<input type="checkbox"/> 9 - UREAD
	<input type="checkbox"/> 10 – SU	<input type="checkbox"/> 11 – CNRS-GAME	<input type="checkbox"/> 12 - CERFACS
	<input type="checkbox"/> 13 – AP	x 14 – UiT	<input type="checkbox"/> 15 - IORAS
	<input type="checkbox"/> 16 - MGO		
Due Date	30 October 2018		
Delivery Date	30 November 2018		
Coordinating authors	Dragana Bojovic, Marta Terrado (BSC)		
Contributing authors	Halldor Johannsson (AP), Isadora Jimenez (BSC), Gerlis Fugmann (APECS), Luisa Cristini (AWI), Thomas Jung (AWI)		

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research & Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 727862.

Table of Contents

Table of Contents 3

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY 4

1. INTRODUCTION 5

 1.1. Background and motivation 5

 1.2. Organisation of the plan 5

2. APPLICATE USER-ENGAGEMENT PLAN 6

 2.1. Short-term activities (conducted during the first project year) 6

 2.2. Mid and long-term activities (from the second year of the project) 8

3. RISKS AND INTERDEPENDENCIES 9

4. IMPLEMENTATION OF THE PLAN 11

 4.1 APPLICATE users 11

 4.2. Implementation of the key user engagement mechanisms 13

4. ACRONYMS 18

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The main objective of the APPLICATE project is to develop enhanced predictive capacity for weather and climate in the Arctic and beyond, and to determine the influence of Arctic climate change on the Northern Hemisphere. To produce usable and trustworthy predictive information for decision making, APPLICATE will actively engage with users, including policy makers, businesses and society within and outside the EU. Only by effectively exchanging information with stakeholders and co-developing knowledge, can we assure the stakeholder-relevance of the project results, which can then enhance their capacity to adapt to long-term climate change.

The proactive dialogue with users will be performed using modern and interactive user engagement mechanisms that will be developed and maintained throughout the project. This updated plan describes already applied engagement approaches and activities, as well as those planned for the rest of the project. It provides a detailed description of the three main user categories defined by the project – key, primary and secondary. It builds around three main mechanisms of user engagement to be applied in the project: i) User Group involvement ii) Participation in meetings and organization of workshops, iii) Case studies development iv) User blog and interviews.

In order to maximize the projects impact in a meaningful, direct and measurable way, specific users have been and will be targeted and involved through the projects User-Group. Further identification of project relevant users, to be consulted and impacted through case-studies and organised events, will be on going.

Project impact on identified specific users will be measured through the stakeholder engagement and collected stakeholder feedback.

In addition, different communication channels that are also being developed and maintained as a part of the project, including the project website, social media channels and project dissemination material, will enhance information exchange and knowledge transfer, presenting the first step towards user engagement and reaching a broad and diverse group of users.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background and motivation

One of the aims of the APPLICATE project is to increase the awareness about the impact of Arctic changes on the weather and climate of the Northern Hemisphere and to adequately convey project results to stakeholders, including any user of climate and weather services. To achieve this, the project will develop relevant and effective forms of communication, cooperation and engagement with projects and stakeholders within and outside the EU. In addition, in order to provide at the same time scientifically robust and user relevant and usable knowledge about the climate and weather in the Arctic, the project needs to maximise exposure of the science produced to different users and collect and consider feedback from them. In order to assure knowledge sharing and exchange with stakeholders and project impact, in this plan we propose different user engagement mechanisms that have been developed and maintained throughout the project.

The terms user and stakeholder are used interchangeably in this plan. Stakeholders or users include all those that can be interested in and/or can benefit from better knowledge of the weather and climate in the Arctic and Northern Hemisphere. By pro-active user-engagement, the latest advances in forecasting system development can be effectively communicated to and benefit those economic sectors and social aspects that rely on improved forecasting capacity.

To develop and conduct targeted user engagement activities, knowledge transfer and exchange, we divide users in three categories:

- 1) Key users – scientific community and intergovernmental organisations
- 2) Primary users – private sector and public sector stakeholders
- 3) Secondary users – general public, society, local communities.

By continuously taking into account user needs and feedback to the APPLICATE results via the User Group, workshops, meetings, interviews with key stakeholders, virtual consultations, and development of case studies, the APPLICATE community will increase the stakeholder-relevance of its research and hence directly improve stakeholders' capacity to adapt to climate change.

1.2. Organisation of the plan

The user-engagement plan is structured around the main proposed mechanisms for user engagement. This includes i) User Group involvement, ii) interactions at workshops, meetings and conferences, iii) development of case studies and iv) user blog and interviews with stakeholders. In addition, user engagement is closely merged with the other two components of WP7 – communication and dissemination of the project results and training. Some of the communication channels, such as the project website and social media, are also very effective tools for user engagement. Moreover, communication is understood as the first step in motivating stakeholders' participation, to be followed by more profound and bi-directional knowledge exchange and engagement approaches. These communication channels will thus be shortly presented in this plan, and elaborated more in depth in the APPLICATE Communication and Dissemination Plan.

2. APPLICATE USER-ENGAGEMENT PLAN

User engagement is an essential part of APPLICATE since the project needs to establish an effective dialogue with a network of key stakeholders in order to obtain feedback to help and improve weather and climate modelling and forecasting. The user engagement plan has been divided in short- and mid/long-term activities.

2.1. Short-term activities (conducted during the first project year)

Activity	Leader	Procedure	Expected outcomes
Project website	AP	The project website is a channel for passive user engagement, where various stakeholders can learn about the project and get in contact. It will continue to be updated throughout the project.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Provide a primary channel for communication about the project. ▪ Present general information on the project, goals and objectives of the various work packages, news and events, dissemination material and project documents. ▪ Provide a clear idea of what users can get from the project (e.g. type of knowledge generated) ▪ Guide users in how to get in touch with the project User engagement team. ▪ Promote all other user engagement activities. ▪ Promote a direct link to the user blog.
Social media campaign	AP	APPLICATE Twitter account and Facebook page are additional channels for both passive and active user engagement.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Provide a channel for a two-way communication with various stakeholders, allowing for posts, comments and replies by users. ▪ Learn about the user feedback and inform further project developments, by regularly moderating and revising the information from our social media channels.
User Group	AP, BSC	Various representatives of key stakeholders have joined the User Group and the list might be enlarged if additional relevant stakeholders are identified. The group includes representatives from different sectors. Users take part in virtual consultations that WP7 coordinators organise on a regular basis. The first face-to-face meeting took place during the Arctic Circle Assembly in 2017, followed by a more-complete group meeting at the project general assembly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Provide an external user-specific perspective and feedback on the relevance and presentation of project outcomes. ▪ Analyse and share feedback with i) user group participants to maintain discussion, and ii) the project partners to help shape project outputs into user relevant products. ▪ Assure timely response and feedback to the project outputs.

		in January 2018. The User Group meetings continued on a regular few months bases.	
Workshops and meetings at professional events	AP, BSC	<p>APPLICATE partners participate in relevant external events or initiatives organized by the target sectors, as well as in scientific conferences. These activities are jointly organized with other relevant projects, such as YOPP, C3S tenders and the EU Arctic Cluster. The list of the events is scheduled in the project calendar on the project website.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Promote and explain the project while interacting with users on different relevant topics. ▪ Broaden and reinforce our understanding of user needs, through feedback from actors not necessarily linked to the weather and climate research communities. ▪ Regularly analyse users’ feedback after each event and i) share it with the project partners, ii) when relevant, share it with other users via User Group and/or Blog or with other projects from the EU Arctic Cluster.
Blog – Polar Prediction Matters	AP, BSC	<p>The project blog is a user engagement tool in the sense that it provides user’s perspectives to the project and at the same time engages other users familiar with the featured topics. The blog is hosted at the Helmholtz Blog website and jointly developed and maintained with YOPP and Blue Action. The content of the blog builds around articles that are regularly published on a monthly basis during the period mid-2017 – mid-2019. These articles present, from different perspectives, climate change in the Arctic, use of climate and weather data and similar topics and have the aim to encourage a discussion with users or other interested parties on the proposed topics. Different stakeholders are in charge of writing the articles with support from APPLICATE, YOPP and Blue Action partners. Although priority will be given to actual users, complementary contributions from people working at operational services, natural and social scientists, science managers and researchers will be also</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Trigger interest of different actors and open discussion on featured topics. ▪ Collect new perspectives on user needs and understandings. ▪ Regularly analyse discussions and inputs in the blog and inform the project partners on any relevant information about user requirements and needs.

		welcome. The discussions will be moderated by the APPLICATE and YOPP's user engagement teams, and supported by the projects' scientists.	
--	--	--	--

All short-term activities will continue throughout the project and are hence relevant also for mid-term and long-term activities.

2.2. Mid and long-term activities (from the second year of the project)

Activity	Leader	Procedure	Expected outcomes
Survey and interviews with users from different stakeholder groups	AP, BSC	<p>We will conduct interviews with representatives of different stakeholder categories and economic sectors of interest. This will take place during the events that we will attend or in separate meetings with users. Alternatively, interviews can also be conducted over the phone/Skype. We will particularly target those communities that are underrepresented in the other user engagement activities, as well as those that express particular interest in the forecast in the Arctic.</p> <p>Surveys will only be conducted if a particular need and a clear research questions emerge. Depending on the aim of the survey, it will be either broadly distributed or targeted at a particular stakeholder category or economic sector. Different communication channels, such as emails, newsletters or social media, will be used to disseminate the survey and collect a large number of responses. In order to avoid user fatigue, we will however aim to obtain this information – such as user relevant metrics – from the existing findings in the other projects and tailor them in the User Group discussions, as well as in the meetings and workshops.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Better understand users' needs and requirements ▪ Analyse and share findings with project partners to shape project outputs and direct further project developments to be in line with user requirements.
Case studies and working groups	AP, BSC	<p>We will develop case studies to show the use of weather and climate forecasts in the case of specific events with significant impact on certain sectors or communities.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Provide clear examples of success stories of using climate data to inform users. ▪ Establish focused, tailored collaboration with a few

		<p>The events to be elaborated in the case studies will be selected together with users, either in User Group meetings or in thematic workshops.</p> <p>Once the topic is decided, we will establish collaboration between a working group, composed of a few users directly related to the particular case study, and the project scientists.</p> <p>Project results and developed case studies will be communicated to various audiences (including European policy makers) in a concise way as short communication materials or factsheets.</p>	<p>users from individual sectors (working groups)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Establish collaboration between a working group and project scientists. ▪ Have a concise way to explain changes in the Arctic and its importance for various users, including European policy makers (with policy factsheets). ▪ Establish an effective communication approach that works for different sectors, such as reindeer herding, fishing, shipping and renewable energy (science- practitioners factsheets). ▪ Further disseminate results within the sectors and communities of the working group participants.
--	--	--	---

3. RISKS AND INTERDEPENDENCIES

Risks and interdependencies are outlined in the table below.

Risk	Probability	Response	Responsibility
Low interest of users	Low/Medium	<p>This risk will be mitigated by using different user engagement mechanisms, such as virtual meetings and consultations. The project will reduce time and travel investments from users and promote their participation.</p> <p>In addition, project partners involved in relevant EU projects, international committees and steering groups can serve as ambassadors for APPLICATE and help disseminate project information and involve stakeholders.</p>	AP and BSC, with support from all project partners
User fatigue	Low	<p>This risk will be addressed by avoiding more “aggressive” user engagement approaches, such as surveys, and encouraging modern, attractive and interactive user engagement mechanisms and communication approaches instead, such as the blog, the User Group, social media, participation and organisation of workshops or discussion tables in relevant events. Coordinating joint user engagement activities with other projects with similar research objectives will in addition lessen the pressure on users.</p>	AP, BSC

Low project visibility	Low	The partners will take part in relevant events presenting the project and getting in touch with different users. These efforts will be organised in strong coordination with other initiatives and projects, such as YOPP, Blue Action, EU Arctic Cluster, IASC and SAON, increasing the projects' visibility, while lowering the risk of user fatigue or confusion with too much information from different projects.	AP, BSC, all partners, partners from other projects
Cultural & background differences	Low	The project partners have a long-term and well-established collaboration with different actors within the Arctic. The project will additionally improve this collaboration and through interchange with different stakeholder categories (e.g. secondary user group) better understand cultural differences, while integrating local knowledge in the project development.	AP, BSC, all partners
Low interest in writing the user blog posts	Low	APPLICATE, YOPP and Blue Action have contacts with numerous stakeholders that might be interested in contributing to blog posts. We will rely on these connections and on contacting participants well in advance, to assure that regular posting on the blog is maintained.	AP, BSC, YOPP, Blue Action
Too low interest of the targeted audience in the user blog	Medium	Developing and maintaining this activity jointly with other projects, such as YOPP and Blue Action, improves the visibility of the blog and interest and participation of different users, decreasing the risk of lack of participation.	AP, BSC, YOPP, Blue Action
Too high interest in the user blog	Low	To maintain a fruitful discussion that can tackle different topics, including scientific ones, we will assure active collaboration of the project scientists on facilitating the blog discussions.	AP, BSC, YOPP, Blue Action, all project partners
Lack of participation of mid-latitude and non-European users	Medium	Building on partners' existing networks and through participation in relevant European and international events, the project will be shared and discussed with stakeholders that are not traditionally interested in the Arctic issues. In this way, we will increase participation of mid-latitude and non-European users.	AP, BSC, all partners

4. IMPLEMENTATION OF THE PLAN

4.1 APPLICATE users

APPLICATE will apply modern user engagement tools for online facilitation and the most efficient channels for information exchange with users. The implementation of the User Engagement plan will build around three main users groups: Key users, primary users and secondary users.

1. Key users

WHO: Key users include the **scientific community and intergovernmental organisations**.

Both benefit from advancements in model development, predictive capacity and understanding of the impact of Arctic changes on the weather and climate of the Northern Hemisphere as well as from educational activities. There is a wide range of beneficiaries, from individual scientists working on related topics to networks of scientists working collaboratively together in networks and projects (e.g. US Sea Ice Prediction Network, US CLIVAR Arctic-Midlatitude Working Group, IPCC). Furthermore, research departments in operational weather and climate prediction centres with an interest in Polar Regions will directly benefit from the project outputs. Enabling development of improved weather and environmental prediction services for the Polar Regions, on different time scales, will for example directly benefit the World Meteorological Organization's Polar Prediction Project within the World Weather Research Programme. APPLICATE project results will also be relevant to scientific community umbrella institutions and projects such as the European Climate Research Alliance and International Arctic Science Committee, as well as to the working groups of the Arctic Council and experts of international organisations like the International Maritime Organisation.

HOW: APPLICATE partners have strong links to these organizations and communities, with many consortium members being directly involved within their activities. Therefore, key users can be approached via e-mail and or in jointly attended meetings and events. By participating in relevant scientific conferences (e.g. EGU, AGU, EMS) and European and international events (e.g. PAMIP and YOPP workshops), APPLICATE scientists promote results of the project and interact with key users.

WHY: Key stakeholders are expected to be advanced users of data. They may often be interested in direct project outputs, models and techniques used to produce data. The main effort is to make this community aware of the project and its results, i.e. to transfer the scientific knowledge produced in the project to them. In this sense, their engagement in APPLICATE will fill the gap in knowledge transfer. In addition, a close collaboration with key users can help the APPLICATE scientists focus on the aspects that are the most needed by this community. In other words, they can indicate the research needs regarding climate change in the Arctic and, at the same time, act as a peer group, providing feedback on the scientific progress of APPLICATE.

2. Primary users

WHO: Primary users include the **private sector** and the **public sector** stakeholders, including policy makers. This category comprises different user profiles, including high-skilled users (e.g. modellers in the energy sector), non-experts that might demand tailored products and services (e.g. decision-makers that should decide whether to apply or not a particular action), and policy-makers. The private sector includes different businesses depending on weather and climate, such as insurance, shipping, tourism, or fisheries, whereas the public sector is constituted by national and regional authorities. Primary users will not be only from the Arctic but also from mid-latitudes.

HOW: The APPLICATE members have strong relations with these stakeholders within Europe, Asia and North America. Primary user representatives, will get involved via interviews, workshops and the User Group and can become effective co-designers of the APPLICATE outputs. Through this collaboration and feedback, the project will aim to incorporate the needs of the public and private sector in the forecasting systems and in the eventual products generated as a result of the project. From the second project year, we will also start working with smaller working groups of users from specific sectors. Working groups will have a strong link with project scientists and will work on the case studies development. In addition, with the support from the project policy officer, we will approach European policy makers. We will target initiatives such as Horizon Europe and EU in the Arctic. The main communication and engagement tool for policy makers will be short communication, case studies and factsheets that we will use to deliver the main project messages (e.g. about the relation between higher frequency of climate extreme events in Europe and changes in the Arctic).

WHY: The **private sector** stakeholders benefit from enhanced operational predictive capacity across time scales. The forecast improvements at hourly-to-decadal timescales developed by APPLICATE will lead directly to improved services for the economic sectors that rely on forecasts. Insurance, shipping, tourism, and fishery industries, among others, are increasingly in need of weather and climate information at these timescales and effective transfer of new knowledge is a crucial component. Active engagement in APPLICATE will help the **public sector** to use the knowledge produced in the project to shape the necessary actions and instruments to address future challenges and make better informed decisions. Direct engagement with primary users will build trust and understanding and incorporate user requests and suggestions in APPLICATE activities, which will eventually provide public and private sector stakeholders with the information they actually need to make well-informed decisions.

3. Secondary users

WHO: The secondary user group refers to **the society at large**, including **the general public and local communities**.

HOW: Different communication channels, applied in APPLICATE, will be used to animate and involve this group. This includes information exchange through the website, social media – the APPLICATE Facebook page and the Twitter account, and the user blog. In particular, with the user blog we will aim to involve this group in an online discussion on different topics related to climate change in the Arctic. More direct engagement with this

group will be achieved through meetings and workshops, particularly with local and indigenous communities. At least one working group with users from local communities will be established from the second year of the project to work on the development of a case study.

WHY: Weather and climate change can have large impacts on the environment and the human society. Climate change and weather extremes are therefore areas of great interest to the global community. Specific communities, however, are more likely to be engaged with specific issues, e.g. indigenous peoples in the Arctic are directly affected by the impacts of regional Arctic climate change. The main outcomes of APPLICATE, that is an improved ability to simulate and predict changes in the Arctic and their impacts on weather and climate of the Northern Hemisphere, will be of great interest to the general public and to certain local communities. This new knowledge, however, needs to be shaped so to be useful and usable for this group. Integrating local knowledge with the scientific findings can bring more holistic and well accepted results, while this knowledge exchange will benefit both scientific and the local and endogenous communities.

4.2. Implementation of the key user engagement mechanisms

Besides the various communication channels that will enable information sharing with users and receiving their feedback (e.g. through social media), the most important user engagement activities applied in this project are the User Group, workshops and meetings, blog, interviews, and working groups for case studies development

User Group

The User Group is a group of 7-10 representatives from the public and private sector (Primary stakeholders). The group meets (virtually or in person) every few months, to discuss the development of the project outputs, with the aim to make them both user relevant and usable. The group supports the project with an external user-specific perspective by providing continuous feedback on the relevance of the results obtained and the way they are presented. Regular feedback from this group assures that the products generated in the project are tailored to user needs, maximising their relevance and usability. The User Group will serve the project as an additional advisory mechanism. The group is coordinated and monitored by AP and BSC. Originally, the User Group was established through personal contacts and project connections (e.g. we contacted those stakeholders who wrote a support letter accompanying the APPLICATE funding application). The group aimed at including stakeholders from around the Arctic and beyond, as well as representatives of relevant sectors and communities. Currently, the user group comprises representatives of: local communities; reindeer herders; shipping industry; icebreaker company; legal, policy and investment organisation; sustainable development research, and international institutions working on Arctic maritime science. After communicating and consulting with the original stakeholder group members and reaffirming their interest and availability to participate in the User Group, we considered together representativeness gaps. We proposed other sectors that should be involved in the User Group, including nature conservation, energy, and tourism. However, despite the numerous invitation emails and personal contacts established (e.g. we contacted different offices of WWF, Greenpeace, and Bellona but without a positive answer), we haven't succeeded to involve some of these sectors yet (e.g. nature conservation). The suggested strategy is to try

to establish these liaisons through other projects within the EU Arctic Cluster or through contact persons in the European Commission (e.g. the project officer). For the energy sector, we will try to establish collaboration with an ERA4CS project in order to explore linkages between the Arctic and mid-latitudes. Also, we will continue looking for new User Group members in the planned sectoral workshops as well as in the events we attend. In the case we cannot involve a certain sector in the User Group we will try to conduct individual interviews with a representative from that sector.

Early User Group discussions were targeting the Arctic as a whole, trying to understand the most pertinent issues for which enhanced weather and climate prediction could be an asset. With the new project results becoming available and providing better insights into the impacts of Arctic change on mid-latitudes, we will enhance liaison with participants from Europe. In particular, issues such as a higher frequency of extreme events in Europe related to Arctic changes and their impact on the energy sector could be of interest.

To assure that the members of the Group are up to date with the latest project achievements, we have been organising “updating” meetings with different WPs. In these meetings, representatives from WP1, WP2, WP3 and WP5 have been discussing with the User engagement team about their latest results and how the project can address user needs. The project researchers are also regularly invited to participate in the User Group meetings. The results from the hitherto user group discussions have been analysed, shared with the user group members, and reported in D7.11, as well as to the project coordination team. In addition, the results have also been disseminated in the form of two brief publications: (i) "Insights from the APPLICATE User Group meeting" in the Polar Journal and (ii) "A changing Arctic – dialogues from the North" in the Adaptation Futures conference proceedings.

Workshops and meetings

Organizing and performing workshops and meetings, and participating in relevant events serve to present the project results to various audiences, including both Arctic stakeholders and stakeholders from mid-latitudes. The project partners participate in relevant external events and carry out workshops and meetings during these events to get direct feedback from a user perspective. These events also include scientific conferences, where we have the chance to meet, discuss with and get feedback from our key stakeholder group. Besides, through participation in the initiatives organized by the target sectors, we will have an opportunity to exchange information and collect feedback from the primary stakeholder group. Finally, by taking part in various relevant events, we will also have the opportunity to meet with the secondary stakeholder group and with the actors not usually linked to the weather and climate research communities.

AP and BSC, together with other project partners, regularly take part in these events. Parallel sessions at these events, in form of workshops, round tables, or splinter sessions have been and will continue to be jointly organized with the EU Arctic Cluster or in collaboration with other relevant H2020 projects, C3S contracts (e.g. the C3S Global Shipping service), or ERA4CS projects (e.g. Clim2Power). This approach will ensure that we get in touch with various audiences and different stakeholders, while preventing user fatigue, through a coordinated action of different projects with the focus on climate change in the Arctic.

The project partners will be encouraged to report on their participation in APPLICATE relevant events and on how they presented the project (e.g. in a scientific session, poster presentation, workshop, informal meeting, or distribution of project material). AP and BSC, with support from other project partners, will collect more concrete feedback from the users encountered in these events. These inputs will be regularly further discussed with the User Group and shared with the project scientists.

Development of case studies with working groups

Case studies will be developed, in a form of storylines, around weather and climate events with significant impact on certain sectors or communities. Case studies aim to demonstrate how we can predict these events or use climate data and information to better understand them. Both User Group meetings and thematic working group meetings and workshops will serve to select relevant case studies. These meetings will be ideally organised in collaboration with the EU Arctic Cluster. In this regard, a workshop for the shipping industry is planned for the next year's Arctic Frontiers conference. In this workshop, we will map the needs for improved weather and climate data for safer operations and smarter decision-making in the Arctic maritime affairs.

The case studies will be developed in working groups. A working group will be composed of a few users from the relevant sector, young researchers involved in the project and the project scientists. While the sectoral users will provide information from the ground – e.g. what information would serve them in the events described in the case study, project researchers will provide examples of what the project can provide in terms of weather and climate prediction information. We will then together analyse the role of climate data and prediction in the selected events and the users will evaluate the usability of such information in their decision-making. Examples of case studies are: an anomalous decrease in sea ice extent in the Arctic with potential impact on energy demand in Europe, or the impact of rain-on-snow events on reindeer feeding.

We will use project results and communicate them in a concise way in the format of brief communication pieces or factsheets. This communication materials will be used for different purposes, starting by explaining Arctic-midlatitude linkages and getting in touch with European policy makers. Factsheets can also present findings from the case studies and in that way, be an effective communication tool to approach different sectors, such as reindeer herding, fishing, shipping and renewable energy. We expect these factsheets to be adopted by the User group and working groups participants to disseminate the information further within their sectors and communities. Given that the climate services field is still in its infancy in the Arctic, we noticed the lack of such materials in the scientific conferences we attended. We expect this short, clear and compact communication pieces to thus be an excellent gateway to broader audiences, helping us improving the visibility of the project and disseminating project results, while at the same time enhancing awareness and the knowledge base within users.

Blog, surveys and interviews with stakeholders

The blog Polar Prediction Matters was set up in collaboration with YOPP and Blue Action and hosted by the Helmholtz Association. The blog serves as an online tool for harnessing user feedback and consulting with a broader stakeholder group and should foster the dialogue

between those that research, develop, and provide polar environmental forecasts and those that use (or could use) polar environmental forecasts to guide their decisions. The joint effort with YOPP and Blue Action helps attract high profile contributors – stakeholders that write the blog posts, and also broad interest of the audience. The blog builds upon the articles that are posted once per month. These articles will provide individual views on how polar climate forecasts (and other environmental information) are actually used, what additional needs exist, and what factors might yet limit the effective use of forecasts. The blog aims to launch a lively discussion with a broad audience. Regular posting on the blog and facilitation of the blog discussion will be performed by the YOPP partners, AP and BSC. The APPLICATE scientists have been invited to take part in the discussion as well. User information collected from the blog will be analysed and reported to the project WPs. The frequency of this analysis will depend on the activities of the blog and the relevance of the topics discussed. If this interactive platform gets momentum, it will both provide an effective channel for the project popularisation and for collecting user feedback.

Targeted interviews with representatives from main stakeholder categories will help collect additional in-depth knowledge on user needs, their understanding and perceptions. This intensive one-to-one approach will also help confirm or further clarify knowledge that we will receive through the described user engagement mechanisms. Face-to-face interviews will be performed at the relevant events attended both by APPLICATE and by stakeholders. Alternatively, interviews will be separately scheduled and conducted either face-to-face or over the phone/Skype, depending on the location and the interviewee's profile. So far, we conducted individual interviews with some of the User Group members. We will continue conducting interviews with representatives of main industry sectors of interest in the Arctic, as well as representatives from the mid-latitudes. The concrete list of interviewees will depend on the findings from the other user engagement activities – we will in particular target those communities that are under-represented (e.g. nature conservation), as well as those that express particular interest in the forecast in the Arctic. Findings from the interviews will be analysed and shared with the project partners. The findings will be used to shape project outputs and direct further project developments to be in line with user requirements.

Should a need for understanding a particular user requirement appear, that cannot be obtained from other user engagement activities and sources, we will conduct an online survey. The survey will have well defined questions and will aim to get information on particular aspects (e.g. type of impact indicator, data resolution). Similarly, if a certain user category is underrepresented in the project (e.g. actors from mid-latitudes) and it cannot be engaged through other user engagement activities, we will conduct a survey targeting this particular group. In this case, AP and BSC will develop, conduct and analyse results from the survey. The survey will be distributed using all available communication channels, professional contacts, emailing lists, newsletters, social media, and websites. The chosen dissemination plan will however depend on the targeted user group. In recent years, understanding the relevance and usability of climate information has become a key research topic, increasing the number of activities exploring this subject directly with users, including many surveys being conducted at the moment. To avoid user fatigue, the survey will be conducted only if the concrete need arises.

Both expert interviews and surveys will follow the confidentiality principles and guidelines and participants will sign a pre-prepared consent form for personal data protection and data

storage. The confidentiality principles are based on rules regarding data protection and the European General Data Protection Regulation.

The Second Summary Report of the Stakeholder Interaction Activities, D7.12, will analyse and present results obtained from all four main user engagement mechanisms (described above).

Results evaluation

We will use the results triangulation (consisting in results co-development with particular users and subsequent validation with a broader community) to evaluate the achieved results. This evaluation approach can be effectively conducted using case studies presented in the form of factsheets. In this way, during the results dissemination activities at different events and occasions, we will try to validate the relevance of the information produced with a broader stakeholder community.

The user engagement plan will be updated in October 2019 .

4. ACRONYMS

AGU – The American Geophysical Union

AP – Arctic Portal

APECS – Association of Polar early career scientists

APPLICATE - Advanced Prediction in Polar regions and beyond: Modelling, observing system design and Linkages associated with a Changing Arctic climate

BSC – Barcelona Supercomputing Center

C3S – Copernicus climate change services

EGU – the European Geosciences Union

EMS – the European Meteorological Society

EU – the European Union

H2020 – Horizon 2020 (EU Research and Innovation programme)

IPCC – Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change

PAMIP – Polar Amplification Model Intercomparison Project

YOPP – the Year of Polar Prediction project